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Monetary policy and inflation shocks: are chaotic behavior inevitable?

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically establish the use of discretionary stabilization policy to curtail inflationary shocks in Nigeria, in order to analyze monetary policy implementation shock effect on inflation shocks in the economy. It explored insights from scholarly arguments on the use of ‘discretion’ and ‘rules’ to resolve monetary policy implementation inefficiencies, which was viewed from the ‘paradox of chaos’ perspective. A vector autoregression (VAR) model was introduced to test the null hypothesis that monetary policy instrument do not exhibited shocks that positively increase inflation shocks in the economy. The results suggested that the monetary authority in Nigeria relied heavily on the use of ‘discretion’, with less consideration for ‘rules’ in the implementation of her proposed stabilization policy. Further, discretionary stabilization policies constrain monetary policy implementation effects to curtail inflationary shocks in the economy, technically instituting chaotic behavior across the observation. Monetary policy instrument such as money supply, bank credit, interest rate and exchange rate all exhibited various weave lengths of shock impact that exuberated the prevailing shock impacts of inflation rate in different positive proportions. More, economic growth related stabilization policy shock, also increase inflation shock but budget deficit stabilization initiatives emitted weak negative shocks that curtailed inflation shocks moderately. Other empirical outcomes have implications for effective monetary policy implementation with policy concerns for policy makers, investors, central bank practitioners of other developing economies and academics.

Keywords: Multiple simultaneous equation, Macroeconomic time series, Price, Monetary policy, issues, rules versus discretion

1. INTRODUCTION

The Monetary policy initiatives to minimize the effect of inflationary shocks on the short-run has been met with weak inconsistent responses that lacked the moral ability to deliver on the mandate in the short-run. This is in retrospect of the fact that expected inflation harms the domestic business cycle activities in the economy with consequences for the overall economic growth (Aboyitungiye, & Mathus, 2021). The curious view instill the need for effective monetary policy adjustments to moderate inflationary shocks in the country (Bandaogo, 2021).

This prevailing monetary economic challenge has led to debates that technically seeks clarification on the central banks effective use of stabilization policy ‘rules’ and ‘discretion’ to tackle inflation challenges in Nigeria. Although practitioners hold the view that hold the view that discretion is optimal (Akosah, Alagidede & Schaling, 2020). Academics insist that tentatively ‘rules’ should lead ‘discretion’ in the quest to curtail inflation in the economy. This is because discretionary stabilization policies constrain monetary policy efficiency to deliver on its mandates to liberate the economy inflationary inconsistencies (BIS 2023).

This is in accordance with the ‘paradox of chaos’, where the monetary authority unconsciously implement stabilization policies that express visible chaotic behaviors that are best controlled by monetary policy rules, besides known implementation rigors (Guevara & Lorenze, 2021). Further, Baptiste and Mathu (2023) suggest that such visible chaotic behaviors may be extinguished through the effective implementation of monetary policy rules. More, other scholars project the view that stabilization policy based on rules are consistent, reliable and effective in planning decisive decision to curtail monetary policy weakness to deliver on its implementation promises to curtail inflation (Baptiste & Mathu, 2023; Guevara & Lorenzo, 2021).

Consequently, we considers the need to study the effective use of monetary policy ‘rules’ and ‘discretion’ by the central bank of Nigeria to manage the prevailing rates of inflation plaguing the economy. The first section of this study expressed the introduction by outlining the insights around the different empirical divides across scholarly views on the subject matter. The second section explored more facts around the empirical insights shared in the introductory section to clarify the bases of the debates. The third section illustrated the empirical perspective of the VAR process, institutively aligning it with empirical bases of the study. The forth section interpreted the observed facts from the empirical results with details on the chaotic behavior of monetary policy authorities on the inefficient use of stabilization policy to curtail inflationary shock over the observation. The fifth section states the conclusion of the study.

2. Literature review

In general, inflation is characterized by a general increase in the cost of living over a short period of time, a case where more money chases fewer goods, with implication for economic prosperity besides central bank stabilization strategies. Although, inflation is define as a persistent rise over time in the average price of goods and services (Bank of Canada, 2021a; 2021b; 2003). Expected inflation can be harmful to the economy, because it encourages behaviour that may inhibit economic growth and reduce the public confidence for the future growth of the economy (Aboyitungiye, & Mathus, 2021). Also, monetary policy should involve the adjustment of the money stock through various means; i.e. money supply, interest rates, exchange rates as well as expectations to influence the levels of economic activity and inflation in the right direction to keep it low and stable (Uchendu, 2002; Cottarelli & Balino, 1994).

This calls for the effective use of monetary policy rules to effectively conduct central bank economic fluctuation activities, especially inflation stabilization, rather than the use of discretion. It defined monetary policy rules as guided recommendations, of an independent central bank, for the effective conduct of monetary policy activities (Chaparro, Guevara & Escot, 2021; Bandaogo, 2021).

It is consistently argued that central banks should conduct stabilization policy systematically with ‘rules’ than ‘discretion’ (Bennett, 2004). This debate on the most suitable policy approach to counter monetary policy challenges in accordance with discretion have generated minimal perception of the situation with less emphasis on rules and more towards discretion (Akosah, Alagidede & Schaling, 2020). Practitioners hold the view that monetary policy rules allegedly constraint stabilization policy flexibility and the monetary authorities would not automate policy to the degree as proposed by rules (BIS 2023; Guevara & Lorenzo, 2021). This is because the process is difficult to align with the real economic time series in relation to the paradox of chaos in economics (Guevara & Lorenzo, 2021). Consequently, it is only the appropriate use of monetary policy rules that can stabilize the economy and eliminate visible chaotic behaviors in economic time series (Baptiste, & Mathu, 2023; BIS, 2023; Guevara & Lorenzo, 2021; Bank of Canada, 2021C; Conttarelli, & Balino, 1994). Scholars in academics upholding the principle that

monetary policy based on rules are effective and credible than discretionary monetary policies, thus academics seeks to abrogate central bank operational strategies linked to discretion that limits its policy initiatives (Baptiste, & Mathu, 2023).

METHODS

In this study we used time series datasets from the period 1970 to 2024 (CBN, 2018; 2020; 2022; 2024 on line database). This permitted us to carry out our analysis long different policy eras within the Nigeria economy as expressed during this period. Thus, these phenomenon may influence the impacts stabilization policy thought specified variables in the model in relation their outcomes on inflation. Consequently, we employed the Vector autoregression technique for the estimation of the model and the estimation process was done using the e-view 10 enterprise edition econometric software.

Model specification

This study adapted the Brainard’s normative impact of economic uncertainty on monetary policy hypothesis, in accordance with the robust policy rules with structured uncertainty (Onatski & Stock, 2000; Brainard, 1967). Specifically, we modified the standard linear-quadratic rules to a non-linear-quadratic rule to encapsulate developing economy realities, adjust for our model unique perturbation and eliminate the weakness of the Brainard’s linear-quadratic rules with the use of a VAR model.

Basically, the functional form of the model for the study is presented thus:

$$INFL = f (MS, BCE, INTR, ECOGW, BDFIT, INFL(t - 1)) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (3.1)$$

Transforming the equation (3.1) to a log linear expression so as to facilitate estimation, the model becomes:

$$Ln INFL = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 LnMs + \alpha_2 LnBCE + \alpha_3 LnINTR + \alpha_4 LnECOG + \alpha_5 LnBD + \alpha_6 LnINFL_{(t-1)} + U_t \quad - \quad - \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

Ln = Logarithm of variables

INF = The rates of inflation

α_0 = Intercept

Ms = Broad money supply

BCE = Credit to the domestic economy

INTR = Interest rate

ECOGW = The Nigeria economy real gross domestic product growth

BDFIT = Budget deficit

$INF_{(t-1)}$ = One period lagged inflation rate

U_t = Stochastic error term

The presumptive (a priori) signs are: $\alpha_1 > 0$, $\alpha_2 > 0$, $\alpha_3 < 0$, $\alpha_4 > 0$, $\alpha_5 > 0$ and $\alpha_6 > / < 0$.

To express these specified variables in equation (3.2) in VAR form, they were further represented in matrix notation as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \eta_t \\ \vdots \\ EP_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_{\eta t} \\ \vdots \\ U_{EPt} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{dd,1} \cdots \psi_{dEP,1} \\ \vdots \\ \psi_{dEP,1} \cdots \psi_{EPEP,1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_{d,t-1} \\ \vdots \\ U_{dEP,t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{dd,2} \cdots \psi_{dEP,2} \\ \vdots \\ \psi_{dEP,2} \cdots \psi_{EPEP,2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_{d,t-2} \\ \vdots \\ U_{EP,t-2} \end{bmatrix} + \cdots \quad - \quad (11)$$

This matrix expresses the polynomial matrix of the VAR relationship between the rate of inflation in the light of stabilization policies that influence economic growth and budget deficit. Note that $\psi_{dd,2}$ represent $\frac{\partial \eta_{t+2}}{\partial u_{d,t}}$, which signifies the responses of the rates of inflation in t-4 time period to a unit innovation in the disturbance term U_d occurring in period t. In accordance with the results of the lag length test (see Appendix A & B), with the consideration that all other innovations in this model over the same observations are held constant (Hamilton, 2009; Hansen, 1995).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The VAR analysis output table in Appendix B, indicated various levels of shock impacts expressed by the variables in the model and their shock relationships are interpreted below:

1. Previous inflation policy shock significantly promoted a reduction in present levels of inflation. This suggest that to a large existing monetary policy administrators basically followed previous existing success policy protocol to tract and curtail prevailing inflation rate in the economy beside existing rule and discretion.
2. Monetary policy instruments administered through money supply emitted significant positive permanent shocks that increase the existing levels of inflation in the economy. This is besides the fact that prevailing monetary policy rule confirmed that administrators should develop a money supply initiative that will culture an inverse permanent shock in inflation rate on the short-run. This suggested that these money supply systems were not adequately planned, prognosticating their inflationary tendencies in accordance with the existing inflation rate stabilization strategies. This illustrates that money policy rules did not guide their stated discretionary monetary policy to adequately control the existing levels of inflation, anticipating the likelihood of the intensity of the unknown shocks in accordance with prevailing known shocks previously observed with minimal likelihood of deviations from the known norms to effectively curb the effect of inflation on the economy.
3. Besides monetary policy rules, the effective use of bank credit policy, by the discretionary initiatives of the central bank, to reduce the impact of inflation on the economy did not indicate obvious tendencies to reduce inflation. These points to the fact that discretionary policy failed to use bank credit as an effective stabilization measure to reduce the inflation rate in the short-run. Consequently, bank credit policy emitted positive permanent shocks that increased existing rates of inflation in the economy.
4. Interest rate policy implemented during this short-run period slacked on its impact to minimize the effect of inflation rate on the economy. This is because it emitted weak positive shocks that spiral the existing rate of inflation positively, beyond the monetary policy discretionary proposed inflation reduction tendencies, into a higher path that is beyond the present monetary policy system control. This is a clear indication of a stabilization strategy flaw that needs intensive rethink to deliver its discretionary policy mandate in accordance with rules, to keep its purpose focused on its goal to effectively use interest rate policy to reduce inflation.
5. The positive permanent shocks from exchange rate on the short-run discretionarily increase the levels of inflation rate in the economy with an impact of 0.0312. This suggested that it emitted light inconsistent positive permanent shock impact that strongly increased the prevailing inflation rate. This deceptive mild case with intense short-run shock impact reflect stabilization policy malfunction that needs technical recalibration in accordance with the expressed stabilization policy rules to lead progress that will curtail inflation through exchange rate policy.
6. Economic growth short-run positive permanent shocks significantly exhibited an impact of 0.1944 that increased domestic inflation rates. This suggested that economic growth strategies designed to technically align macroeconomic fundamental to reduce inflation and drive business cycle activities, generated misleading shock signals with consequences for the integrity of dynamic stabilization lead structural policy.
7. Budget deficit emitted slightly moderate inverse cross permanent shock asymmetry with an impact of -0.0775 that tactically reduce the levels of inflation rate in the domestic economy on the short-run.

Although this variable is not significant, it gives valuable insights that projects government precautionary borrowing to finance future development projects today, as a panacea to tackle increasing inflation on the short-run in anticipation of its unfavourable long-run tendencies as a result of the consistent increase in exchange rate and other transitory cost.

CONCLUSION

We empirically analyzed monetary policy shock impacts on existing inflationary shocks in the Nigeria economy from 1970 to 2024, in order to identify the strength of monetary authority's effective use of discretionary stabilization policy to curtail the persisting inflation in the economy. The VAR econometric technique was used to reveal the impact of these shocks and disclose the strength of the selected policy to curtail inflationary tendencies in the economy. The results indicated that in accordance with protocol, previous inflation policies were used as bench mark to successively promote a reduction in present levels of inflation as a matter of rules but this was not the case with other monetary instruments over the observation studied. This is because the stabilization policy further relied heavily on discretionary policies during the implement process across the observation.

Consequently, shocks from monetary supply adjustments exhibited positive shocks that increased inflationary shocks in the economy. Bank credit policy shocks increased inflation shock and interest rate policy shocks also increased inflation shock during these periods. Similarly, other stabilization policy instruments like exchange rate policy basically increased the level of inflationary shocks in the economy over time. Monetary authority's use of economic growth target policy to drive their projected plans to curtail inflation shocks exhibited shocks that increased the shocks indicated by the present levels of inflation in the economy. The case of budget deficit was different, it revealed weak permanent shocks that reduced inflation shocks across the observation.

The weakness of these established monetary policy instruments to curtail the effect of inflationary tendencies to a high degree, has made it inevitable for these stabilization tools to exhibited sets of chaotic behaviors. This clearly illustrates that the present system is plagued by the 'paradox of chaos', in a case were the monetary authorities use discretionary policy systems ineffectively without considering established rules to guide the implementation processes needs to be taken seriously by both the monetary authorities, policy makers and scholars in the academia. Therefore, this is a wakeup call to restructure the policy need for the system to reconsider the use of rules for effective inflation economic rescue planning in order to drive stabilization policies that will efficiently direct the financial system to encourage better economic growth prospects. From these views shared above, it is clear that the monetary authorities in Nigeria heavily relied on discretionary monetary policy, over the observation, which did not lead its projected inflationary policy targets and they were not consistent in the short-run.

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